

Species 1: *H. ethilla*

NOT test

Species 2: *H. numata*

Environmental overlap

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
D = 0.374

Background 2→1

Background 1→2

Species 1: *H. ethilla*

NDT test

Species 2: *H. numata*

Environmental overlap

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
D = 0.373

Background 2->1

Background 1->2

